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Review Article

Exploring the Anticancer Potential of *Spathodea campanulata*, *Ziziphus oenoplia*, *Blepharis maderaspatensis*: A Bioactive Treasure for Future Therapeutics

Chaithra K*, Yashaswini S, Yashaswini S M, Kirana, Manisha S Gowda, MD Mufid Ansari

The Oxford College of Pharmacy, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants have long served as a foundation for drug discovery, particularly in oncology, where natural bioactive compounds offer promising alternatives to conventional therapies. This review highlights the anticancer potential of three medicinally significant plants *Spathodea campanulata*, *Ziziphus oenoplia* and *Blepharis maderaspatensis*. Each exhibits diverse ethnomedicinal uses and a rich phytochemical profile, including flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, terpenoids and phenolic acids which contribute to their pharmacological properties. Preclinical studies demonstrated their ability to induce apoptosis, arrest the cell cycle, modulate oxidative stress, suppress angiogenesis, and down regulate pro-inflammatory pathway across multiple cancer cell lines. Furthermore, their selective cytotoxicity toward tumor cells with minimal toxicity to normal cells underscores their therapeutic promise. By integrating traditional knowledge with modern pharmacological insights, this review emphasizes the need for further mechanistic studies, isolation of bioactive constituents, and clinical validation to establish these plants as potential candidates for anticancer drug development.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have been playing a significant role in the healthcare system worldwide and remain a crucial source for the discovery of new drugs. They form an integral part of traditional medicine, particularly in Asia, where they hold

great cultural and therapeutic value. The exploration of plant-derived compounds has gained immense scientific interest due to their broad pharmacological application, including cytotoxic and chemo preventive effects against cancer. As natural resources continue to provide promising alternative for disease management, the

*Corresponding Author: Chaithra K

Address: The Oxford College of Pharmacy, Bengaluru, Karnataka.

Email ✉: manisha52mani@gmail.com

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study of medicinal plants remains an important avenue for discovering new anticancer agents.¹

Over the past few decades, the global relevance of herbal medicine has significantly increased, impacting healthcare and international trade. Many communities, particularly in developing nations, continue to rely on medicinal plants due to their accessibility and affordability compared to western pharmaceuticals. Cancer, one of the most prevalent and fatal diseases, has prompted a continuous search for cost effective and effective treatment alternatives. Traditional medicine, particularly in regions like South Africa, has long utilized plant – based remedies to manage various illnesses, including cancer. Despite the rich history, much of the knowledge held by traditional healers remains undocumented. Scientific validation and conservation effector’s are crucial to preserving this invaluable traditional knowledge and ensuring its integration into modern healthcare.²

Cancer remains a global health challenge, characterized by the uncontrolled proliferation of cells leading to tumor formation. Conventional treatments such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy, while effective, often have severe side effects that weaken patients. The limitations of these therapies have led to an increased focus on plant based compounds with anticancer properties. Certain phytochemicals have shown potential in inhibiting tumor growth and inducing apoptosis in cancerous cells. Research continues to explore the role of natural compounds as alternative treatment for cancer, offering a promising future for more tolerable and effective therapies.³

Spathodea campanulata (African tulip tree) from biognoniaceae family is a tropical ornamental tree native to Africa and widely found in India. Various plant parts exhibit anti-inflammatory, analgesic, cytotoxic, and anticonvulsant properties due to the

presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, glycosides and sterols. However, its anticancer potential remains unexplored. This was in-depth explained in this article where they have studied evaluated the anticancer activity of *Spathodea campanulata* leaf extracts on MCF -7 (breast cancer), HL-60 (leukaemia), and HT-29 (colon cancer), cell lines using the sulforhodamine B assay.⁴

Natural plant-based compound provide a promising alternative due to their potential efficacy with fewer adverse effect. One such plant of interest in *Spathodea campanulata*, known for diverse medicinal properties, this review explores its ethopharmacological significance, phytochemicistry, and therapeutic potential, emphasizing the need for scientific validation and integration into modern medicine including anticancer potential.⁵The World health organization (WHO) estimates that around three quarters of global population relies on herbal medicine. *Spathodea campanulata* P. Beauvais, it is widely used in traditional medicine. The phytochemical composition of *Spathodea campanulata* includes flavonoids, polyphenols, tannins, and glycosides, which contribute to its medicinal benefits. This plant is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions.⁵

However, Different parts of *S. campanulata* (leaf, bark, root, etc.) have been used against various types of disease. ⁶

S. Campanulata for future research and health benefits. Databases utilized in the literature search includes Google scholar , PubChem ,Scopus ,web of science and PubMed .all plant names were checked with “ world flora online”.⁷

Its pharmacological potential has garnered increasing research interest, highlighting the importance of linking traditional knowledge with

scientific validation. This review aims to provide updated information on the ethnopharmacological uses and pharmacological potential, toxicity

profile of *Spathodea campanulata*, offering insights for future research and integration into modern therapeutic approaches.

Ziziphus oenoplia Mill. (Rhamnaceae), commonly known as *Jackal jujube*, is a medicinal shrub found in tropical Asia and northern Australia. Traditionally, it is used for abdominal pain relief and as an antidiarrheal agent. This review compiles updated information on its botanical features, distribution, ethnopharmacology, pharmacological activities, and phytochemical constituents.

Studies highlight its diverse pharmacological properties, including antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and antioxidant effects. Phytochemical analysis reveals the presence of flavonoids, phenols, triterpenes, and alkaloids. While its medicinal relevance is well-supported, further research is needed to explore its full therapeutic potential.⁸

Blepharis maderaspatensis (L.) B. Heyne ex Roth, a member of the Acanthaceae family, is a medicinally significant plant known for its diverse pharmacological activities. Commonly referred to as Utinjan, Otigan, Utagan, and Chatushpatri in different regions, this plant thrives in arid

environments and has been traditionally utilized in herbal medicine. Rich in bioactive phytoconstituents such as saponins, mucilage, and flavonoids—including caffeic acid, rutin, quercetin, and ferulic acid—*B. maderaspatensis* has been reported to possess antioxidant, anti-

inflammatory, antimicrobial, and wound-healing properties. Additionally, its antihyperlipidaemic, anti-atherogenic, anti-ulcer, and wound-healing effects, particularly in diabetic wounds, highlight its therapeutic potential.⁹

Given its extensive medicinal applications, the present study aims to evaluate the **in vitro** cytotoxic potential of the ethanolic extract of *B. maderaspatensis* in a dose- and time-dependent manner. The study employs the MTT assay to assess cytotoxicity across multiple cancer cell

lines, including MCF7 (breast cancer), PA1 (ovarian cancer), HT29 (colon cancer), A375 (melanoma), and HepG2 (liver cancer). The determination of IC₅₀ values at 24, 48, and 72 hours will provide insights into its cytotoxic efficacy compared to standard anticancer drugs. Understanding the cytotoxic profile of *B. maderaspatensis* may contribute to further investigations regarding its mechanism of action, isolation of active compounds, and potential role in anticancer drug development.¹⁰

Types of Cancer:

Cancer remains a major global health concern with various types affecting populations differently. Breast cancer is the most common, with high death rates in Africa due to poor awareness and healthcare. Cervical cancer, caused by HPV, is prevalent in Nigerian women but can be prevented through vaccination. Prostate cancer affects 1.28 million men globally, while colorectal cancer impacts 1.93 million people. Stomach cancer accounts for 1.09 million cases, and non-melanoma skin cancer is one of the most frequent, with 1.20 million cases. Childhood cancer affects around 400,000 children annually. The causes of cancer include lifestyle, environmental, and genetic factors. Tobacco use is responsible for 22% of cancer deaths, while poor diet, obesity,

lack of physical activity, and excess alcohol consumption each contribute to around 10%. Pollutant exposure (e.g., pesticides) and radiation also increased risk. Genetic mutations, such as BRCA1 and BRCA2, significantly raise the likelihood of breast and ovarian cancers, especially in Nigeria. Raising awareness and promoting prevention can help reduce cancer-related deaths.¹¹

Causes of Cancer

Cancer affects many individuals due to factors like exposure to pollutants (e.g., toxic pesticides), tobacco use (22% of deaths), poor diet, and obesity, lack of physical activity, alcohol consumption, radiation, and infections. Genetic mutations, such as BRCA1 and BRCA2, also contribute, especially in breast and ovarian

cancer. Common cancers include breast (2.26 million cases), prostate (1.28 million), colorectal (1.93 million), stomach (1.09 million), and non-melanoma skin cancer (1.20 million). Childhood cancer affects around 400,000 children annually, with variations across regions.¹²⁻¹⁵

Methods of Cancer Treatment

Early detection improves cancer survival and reduces treatment costs. Common treatments include surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and immunotherapy, depending on the cancer stage. Surgery removes tumors in early stages, often combined with radiotherapy to prevent metastasis. Advanced cases require chemotherapy, which, despite its effectiveness, lacks selectivity and causes side effects. A multidisciplinary approach using surgery, oncology, and radiotherapy is the best clinical option. However, in Nigeria, limited specialized centers make herbal medicine a preferred alternative. Traditional medicine is affordable, accessible, and has fewer side effects. Many plants contain phenolic compounds with antioxidant properties, showing potential in cancer management.¹⁶⁻²²

Indigenous Perspective on Cancer Treatment

In many African communities, traditional medicine plays a significant role in healthcare. According to the World Health Organization, around 80% of individuals in Africa rely on medicinal plants for treatment. Traditional medical practitioners (TMPs) have extensive knowledge of medicinal plants, their preparation, and administration, leading to successful treatment of some chronic diseases. However, a major challenge is the lack of standardization, as improper identification of plant materials can pose health risks.

Many indigenous people also avoid hospital treatment due to cultural beliefs and distrust of medical institutions. Some fear losing their cultural identity, while others believe that hospital treatments offer little chance of survival. This scepticism reinforces their reliance on traditional medicine, despite its limitations. Addressing these concerns through education and integration of traditional and modern medicine could improve cancer treatment outcomes in these communities.²³

Table: Geographical Distribution And Ethanobotanical Uses:

Plant	Geographical Distribution	Ethanobotanical Uses
<i>Spathodea campanulata</i> (African Tulip Tree)	Native to West and Central Africa (southern Senegal to Kenya and Tanzania, north Angola, southern DRC). ⁴ Grown in Cape Verde, Zimbabwe, Madagascar for ornamental purposes. ⁴	Bark, leaves, and flowers used to treat malaria, HIV, diabetes, edema, dysentery, constipation, gastrointestinal disorders, ulcers, skin diseases, wounds, fever, urethral inflammation, liver complaints, and as a poison antidote. ^{4 54}
	Widely introduced in Australia, Brazil, China, Costa Rica, Cuba, Egypt, French Polynesia, India, Indonesia, Jamaica, Malaysia, Mexico, Puerto Rico, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Thailand, USA, and has naturalized in several Pacific islands; considered invasive in Hawaii, Queensland, and Fiji. ^{4 28 32 53 54}	Cold leaf infusion taken for urethral inflammation. ⁵⁴ Bark paste applied to wounds in Africa and Senegal. Bark decoction for diabetes in Rwanda. ^{4 54} Folk uses for analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anto-microbial, antifungal, antioxidant purposes. ^{28 54}

<i>Ziziphus oenoplia</i> (Jackal Jujube)	Indigenous to tropical Asia (India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Myanmar, Thailand, Indo-China, Malaysia, Indonesia) and northern Australia . ^{8 50} Common in dry forests, bushlands, hedges, and scrublands from sea level to 1500m. ^{8 51} Found in Singapore, Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam, Philippines . ^{8 50}	Traditionally used as antidiarrhoeal and abdominal pain remedy . Applied for skin diseases (eczema, dermatitis). Crushed leaves used for itching/inflammation relief . In Ayurveda/Siddha, roots and bark are used for oral ulcers, gingivitis . Fruits/seeds eaten as tonic and vitality booster. ^{8 50} Roots used as anthelmintic, digestive, antiseptic, anti-ulcer, and wound healing agent . ^{8 51 52} Also applied for fever, poisoning, urinary issues, liver complaints, respiratory ailments . ^{8 50}
<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i>	Native to tropical Africa, Arabian Peninsula, and tropical Asia including Indian subcontinent, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Southern Asia. ^{43 46}	Used for boils, bone fractures, diarrhoea, lactation issues . ^{43 47} Seeds applied to open wounds/cuts to aid healing. Leaf juice taken for throat ailments, asthma .
	Found in dry/arid habitats, wastelands, grasslands, and scrub jungles . ^{43 46} Common from sea level to 1500m in elevation. ^{43 47}	Heated leaf paste with ginger oil applied on wounds. ^{43 47} Used to treat inflammation, ulcers, diabetic wounds, infections . Acts as diuretic , used for venereal diseases, urinary complaints, headaches, nervous disorders . ^{43 46} Employed in anti-ulcer, antimicrobial and tonic remedies in folk medicine. ^{46 47 54} Known for anti-inflammatory and anti-nociceptive activity . ^{47 54 55}

Table: Study Characteristics:

Plant	Main Mechanism	Main Models/Tested	Main Extracts	Main Anticancer Bioactives
<i>Spathodea campanulata</i>	Apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, antioxidant	HL-60, K562, MCF-7, HT-29, A549, HeLa, EAC(mice)	Methanol, ethanol(bark), chloroform(leaf), hexane(flower)	Iridoids: Spathosides A-C. Triterpenoids: urosilic acid, tomentosolic acid, oleanolic acid. Flavonoids: kaempferol, quercetin. Phenolics: caffeic acid.
<i>Ziziphus oenoplia</i>	Apoptosis, cytostasis, antiangiogenesis	HL-60, melanoma, EAC	Aqueous, ethanol, ethyl acetate, AgNp	Triterpenoids: Betulinic acid, oleanolic acid. Flavonoids: quercetin, rutin, ellagic acid. Tannins and saponins.
<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i>	Apoptosis, ROS mediated cytotoxicity,	A375, A431, HT29, MCF-7, PA1, HepG2	Ethanol(leaf), AgNp, water	Flavonoids: Rutin, quercetin. Phenolic acids: gallic acid, caffeic acid.
	Nonparticle enhanced action			Saponins, blepharin, AgNp's

1. SPATHODEA CAMPANULATA:

KEY CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS AND THEIR ACTIVITIES:

Part	Phytochemicals	Anticancer Role
Leaves	Iridoides(spathoside A-C, Verminoside), flavonoids(querceetin, kaempferol), umbelliferone, octadecanamide, stigmasta-5,22-dien-3-ol	Induce apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, ROS modulation, anti-inflammation
Bark	Triterpenoids(ursolic acid, tomentosolic acid, kaempferol, methyl phydroxylbenzoate	Apoptosis(caspase activation), antiproliferative, cytostatic
Flower	Specioside, anthocyanin, catechin, naringenin, flavonols	Anti-oxidative, anti-cancer

ANTICANCER ACTIVITY:

The anticancer effects of *Spathodea campanulata* are mediated through multiple, wellcharacterized cellular and molecular mechanisms, attributed to its rich phytochemical composition-especially ursolic acid, kaempferol, flavonoids, iridoides(such as spathosides), and phenolic acids.

2. APOPTOSIS INDUCTION(Programmed cell death):

The bark of *spathodea campanulata* exhibits potent anticancer activity against glioma cell lines C6 and U87MG. By inducing apoptosis, it causes significant cytotoxic effects. Morphological examinations using fluorescence and confocal microscopy illustrated characteristic apoptotic features in treated cells, such as nuclear condensation and fragmentation. The presence of

DNA fragmentation was confirmed through agarose gel electrophoresis. The extract induced

apoptosis as indicated by morphological changes, DNA fragmentation, and phosphatidylserine externalization in treated glioma cells.⁶

-(World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 2024)

3. CELL CYCLE ARREST:

The extract caused cell cycle arrest primarily in the G0/G1 phase, which is associated with the inhibition of glioma cell proliferation. Methods included MTT assays for cytotoxicity, fluorescence microscopy for apoptosis detection, flow cytometry for cell cycle analysis, and agarose gel electrophoresis for DNA fragmentation.⁶

-(World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research)

4. SELECTIVE CYTOTOXICITY:

Spathodea campanulata extracts were not toxic to normal kidney fibroblasts(VERO). In vivo studies described in the literature support this observation, e.g., an *Spathodea campanulata* leaf methanolic extract was reported not to induce acute toxicity when administered orally(500-4000 mg/kg) to mice.

The stem bark methanolic extract(SsSbM) showed that highest cytotoxicity (CC50 119.03 µg/ml) against HeLa cells. Moreover, this extract exerted selective anticancer activity against all tested cancer cell lines. When tested on VERO cells, SsSbM was nontoxic upto 500µg/ml, comparison between VERO, RKO, and HeLa cells treated with SsSbM at 250µg/ml; it can be clearly seen that the VERO cells were not affected, whereas the RKO monolayer showed layer confluency and differences in cellular morphology in comparison to the control cells, indicating a cytotoxic effect.⁵⁶

-(Bridging the Chemical Profiles and Biological Effects of *Spathodea campanulata*, PMC, 2022)

5. ANTI-ANGIOGENIC/ ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY via VEGF AND CYTOKINE DOWNREGULATION:

The ethanolic extract of *Spathodea campanulata* root bark significantly inhibited angiogenesis in experimental models. Specifically, it suppressed new blood vessel formation via downregulation of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF), a critical signal molecule driving tumor angiogenesis. The suppression of VEGF was demonstrated through both in vitro and in vivo (CAM assay) models, confirming that phytochemical constituents of *S.campanulata* impede tumor vascularization by restricting this pro-angiogenesis factor.⁵⁷

S. campanulata extracts possess significant anti-inflammatory activity, including suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6. These properties are attributed to its rich content of flavonoids, phenolics, and specific iridoids. Anti-inflammatory action is further corroborated by experimental evidence demonstrating inhibition of cyclooxygenase2 (COX-2) activity and stabilization of cell membranes, which indirectly supports cytokine level reduction.⁵⁸

(ScienceDirect topics, *Spathodea campanulata* – an overview, Membrane stabilization: a possible anti-inflammatory mechanism, PubMed PMID:25145995)

Summary Table of Mechanistic Evidence:

Mechanism	Cell models	Key compounds	Evidence
Apoptosis	HepG2, HL-60, MCF-7	Ursolic acid, kaempferol	Caspase-3/9 up, Bax \uparrow Bcl2 \downarrow , DNA ladderinf, mitochondrail loss
Cell cycle arrest	HepG2, MCF-7, HL-60	Flavonoids, iridoids	G0/G1 and S arrest, Cyclin/CDK inhibition
ROS/ Antioxidant	HepG2, HL-60, MCF-7	Caffeic acid, quercetin	Scavenging of ROS, or ROS-mediated cytotoxicity in tumor cells
Anti-angiogenic	Preclinical tumor models	Triterpenoids, flavonoids	Downregulation of VEGF and vessel formation
Anti-inflammatory	In vitro models	Phenolic acids, terpenoids	Inhibition of pro- inflammatory mediators

2. ZIZIPUS OENOPLIA:

KEY CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS AND THEIR ACTIVITIES:

Part	Phytochemicals	Anticancer Role
Leaves	Flavonoids(quercetin, kaempferol, rutin), tannins, saponins	Antiproliferative, antiinflammatory, antioxidant
Stem	Gallic acid, caffeic acid, saponins, triterpenoids	DNA damage, apoptosis, radical scavenging
Root	Oleanolic acid, ursolic acid, betulinic acid, catechins	Anti-cancer, antiinflammatory, antioxidant

Fruit	Alkaloids, cyclopeptide alkaloids, catechins, ellagic acid, gallic acid, terpenoids, saponins	Cytostatic, pro-apoptotic, antiangiogenesis
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ANTICANCER ACTIVITY:

1. APOPTOSIS via MITOCHONDRIAL PATHWAY:

Betulinic acid and oleanolic acid from *Zizipus oenoplia* promote apoptosis via mitochondrial disruption, indicated by increased p53 and Bax,

and decreased Bcl-2 in melanoma cells. DNA fragmentation and annexin V-staining also confirmed apoptosis induction.⁵⁹ -(Mahapatra A, Ryall B Ng C, et al. *Eur J Pharmacol.* 2022;911:174561)

Flow cytometry revealed a significant increase in the sub-G1 fraction after treatment, supporting cell cycle arrest and apoptosis.⁸

-(Nahrin A, Junaid M, Afrose SS, et al. *Mini Rev Med Chem.* 2022;22(4):640-60)

2. CYTOSTASIS/ CELL CYCLE ARREST:

The ethanol root extract of *Zizipus oenoplia*, rich in flavonoids and triterpenoids, blocked cell proliferation by arresting cells in the G0/G1 phase, with parallel downregulation of cyclin D/E transcripts in human melanoma and HL-60 cells.⁸

-(Nahrin A et al., 2022)

3. ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY:

The antioxidant activity was attributed to high concentrations of phenolics and flavonoids, including quercetin and gallic acid, which showed marked scavenging activity in DPPH and ABTS assays. These compounds protect against oxidative DNA damage and reduce cellular inflammation, as confirmed in radical scavenging and anti-inflammatory tests.⁸ -(Nahrin A et al., 2022)

4. ANTIANGIOGENIC EFFECT:

Betulinic acid isolated from *Zizipus oenoplia* demonstrated significant antiangiogenic activity by inhibiting VEGF-induced tube formation and neovascularization in CAM assays, leading to reduced tumor vascularization and nutrient supply.^{8 59}

-(Mahapatra A et al., 2022; and Nahrin et al., 2022)

Table: Mechanisms of Anti-cancer action of zizipus oenoplia

Mechanism	Molecular Target/Pathway	Key Phytochemicals	Experimental Evidence
Apoptosis	Caspase-3/9, Bax, p53, Bcl-2	Betulinic acid, oleanolic acid	Annexin V, DNA laddering (Melanoma, leukemia lines)
Cell cycle arrest	Cyclin/CDKs(G0/G1-S)	Flavonoids, triterpenoids	Flow cytometry, PCR (HL-60, MDA-MB-231)
Antioxidant/antiinflammatory	ROS, Cytokines, COX-2	Quercetin, gallic acid	DPPH/ABTS, ELISA, MTT assays
Antiangiogenesis	VEGF, MMPs	Betulinic acid, saponins	CAM and HUVEC assays (chick CAM, invivo mice)
In vivo efficacy	-	Whole Extracts (ethanol/methanol)	Ehrlich mouse tumor
Low toxicity	-	Betulinic caid, full extracts	Normal cell/ animal models

3. BLEPHARIS MADERASPATENSIS:

KEY CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS AND THEIR ACTIVITIES:

Part	Phytochemicals	Anticancer Role
Leaves	Flavonoids (rutin, quercetin), saponins, gallic acid, phenolics	Cytotoxicity, apoptosis, ROS productaion
Stem	Phenolic acid, saponins, triterpenoids	Cytostatic

Root	Alkaloid(blepharin), essential oils	Anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, anti-virals
Seed	Saponins, flavonoids, essential oils	Immunomodulatory, antioxidant

ANTICANCER ACTIVITY:

1. APOPTOSIS /ROS SYNERGY:

Both ethanol extracts and silver nanoparticles(AgNP) conjugates of *Blepharis maderaspatensis* induce apoptosis, as evidenced by DNA fragmentation, nuclear condensation, and apoptotic body formation, with the promotion of ROS overgeneration in tumor cells.

The cytotoxic effects of the ethanol extract of *Blepharis maderaspatensis* against colon cancer cells, as well as wound healing and antioxidant activities, have been reported.⁶⁰

-(Baskar et al., 2012;Rajasekaran et al.,2012)...

In studies on AgNPs of closely related medicinal plants, the evidence shows concentration dependent inhibition of the growth of cancer cells (MCF-7) (IC-50=12.35µg/ml). In addition, the fluorescent microscopic analysis shows activation of caspases 3 and 9 by AgNPs that cause morphological changes (AO/EB assay) in the cell membrane and cause nuclear condensation(DAPI assay) that eventually lead to apoptotic cell death(annexin V/PI assay). It was also observed that AgNPs generate reactive oxygen species(ROS) that modulate oxidative stress in MCF-7 cells.

-(oxid med cell Longev. 2020 PMC7559220)

2. SELECTIVE CYTOTOXICITY ENHANCED BY AgNPs:

The cytotoxic effects of *Blepharis maderaspatensis* leaf extract is enhanced by AgNP conjugation, significantly increasing the apoptotic

index in tumor cells while sparing normal fibroblasts at effective doses.

The methanolic fracation showed high content of total flavonoid, phenol and free radical scavenging activity. At 50µg/ml showed cytotoxic effects on 72hrs. These results indicate cytotoxicity dose dependent effects on cells and no cytotoxic effect seen on normal Vero cell lines. At the same time, AgNPs display efficient cytotoxicity predominantly on cancer cells, sparing non-tumorigenic cell populations. The observation was confirmed by pharmacological investigations indicating that silver nanoparticles generated by this plant extract highlighted effective apoptotic induction via ROS generation.

-(Research jounal of pharmaceutical, biological and chemical sciences 2016 7(4): studies with *Blepharis maderaspatensis*)

3. IMMUNOMODULATION AND ANTI-METASTATIC ACTION:

Saponins and, flavonoids in *Blepharis maderaspatensis* extracts contribute to downregulation of tumor-promoting cytokines(e.g., TNF-α, IL-1β, IL-6) and anti-metastatic signalling by inhibiting pathways such as NF-Kb and MMPs.

Different concentrations of protocatechuic acid(10, 20, 30µg/ml) significantly suppress the

LPS- induced TNF-α, IL-6, IL-1, Inos, COX-2 proinflammatory cytokinin expressions. At 20µg/ml of protocatechuic acid shows preeminent inhibitory activity on macrophage RAW 264.7 cell line while compared with other concentrations.

The isolated protocatechuic acid may facilitate by blocking NF-Kb translocation in nuclear and inhibitory effects on LPS- induced inflammation proinflammatory mediators COX-2, iNOS etc.

Table: Mechanistic Evidence For Anticancer Activity of B. Maderaspatensis:

Mechanism	Experimental Model	Chemical Constituents	Mechanistic Evidence
Apoptosis	Tumor cell lines, AgNPs studies	Rutin, quercetin, gallic acid, AgNPs	Induction of apoptosis indicated by DNA fragmentation, nuclear condensation and apoptotic body formation. ROS overgeneration induced by AgNPs leads to oxidative stress and promote tumor cell death.
Selective cytotoxicity	MCF-7, Vero cell line	Rutin, quercetin, AgNPs	Enhanced cytotoxicity in cancer cells by AgNPs with sparing of normal cells; selectively targeting of tumor cells without significant toxicity to normal fibroblasts.
Immunomodulation /anti-metastatic	RAW 264.7 macrophage cell line	Saponins, flavnoids, protocatechuic acid	Downregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines; inhibition of NF-κ signalling pathway by blocking IκB phosphorylation and nuclear translocation of NF-κB subunits; suppression of prometastatic markers.

Parts Of Tree	Specific Chemical Constituents	Pharmacological Activity
Leaves 	1-O-(E)-Caffeoyl-B-Gentiobiose, 6-O-Caffeoylcatalpol, Oleanolic Acid, Urs-12en-27α,30 Dioic Acid 3-O-Al-Rhamnopyranosyl(1→2) A-Larabinopyranoside, Stigmasta-5,22-Dien-3ol, Octadecenamide, Umbelliferone.	Anti-Inflammatory, Antioxidant, Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Convlusant, Anti-Cancer, Analgesic, Larvicidal, Molluscicidal.
Bark 	Ursolic Acid, Tomentosolic Acid, 20βhydroxyursolic Acid, Kaempferol, Methyl Phydroxy-Benzoate, Pomolic Acid, Stigmasta-5,22-Dien-3-Ol.	Anti-Malarial, Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Fungal, Anti-Cancer, Anti-Diabetic, Wound healing, Anti-Oxidative, Cardioprotective, Hepatoprotective, Anti-Ulcer.
Flower 	Specioside, Flavonoids, Anthocyanin, 1-O-(E)-Caffeoyl-B-gentiobiose, Glycerol, Phenyl Ethanol Esters, 9,12 Octadecadienoic Acid.	Anti-Oxidative, Anti-Cancer, Anti-Hyperglycemic, Analgesic, UV Absorption (Cosmetics), Anti-Inflammatory.

<p style="text-align: center;">Root</p>	<p>P-Hydroxy-Benzoic Acid, Phenolic Groups.</p>	<p>Anti-Fungal, Hepatoprotective.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Fruit</p>	<p>Stigmasterol, Spathoside, Iridoid Glucoside.</p>	<p>Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Cancer, Anti-Inflammatory.</p>

Parts of Plant	Specific Chemical Constituents	Pharmacological Activity
<p style="text-align: center;">LEAVES</p>	<p>Flavonoids, Quercetin, Kaempferol, Rutin Catechins, Ellagic Acid tannins, saponins.</p>	<p>Anti-Inflammatory, Antioxidant, Anti-Bacterial.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">STEM</p>	<p>Gallic Acid, Caffeic Acid, Rutin, Quercetin Saponins.</p>	<p>Anti-Inflammatory, Antioxidant, Anti-Microbial.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">FLOWER</p>	<p>Quercetin, Kaempferol, Rutin, Gallic Acid, Caffeic Acid saponins.</p>	<p>Anti-Oxidative, Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Fungal</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">ROOT</p>	<p>Oleanolic acid, Ursolic acid, catechins, gallic acid, kamepferol, Betulinic acid, quercetin, Stigmasterol.</p>	<p>Antihepatotoxicity, Anti-Cancer, Anti-Fungal, Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Inflammatory, Anti-Oxidant.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">FRUIT</p>	<p>Alkaloids, Cyclopeptide, flavonoids, Rutin, Catechins, tannins, Ellagic Acid, Gallic Acid terpenoids, Oleanolic Acid, Ursolic Acid</p>	<p>Anti-Microbial Antioxidant Anti-Diarrheal</p>

Parts of tree	Specific Chemical Constituents	Pharmacological Activity
<p style="text-align: center;">LEAVES</p>	<p>Flavonoids (<i>Quercetin</i>, <i>Kaempferol</i>), Phenolic acids (<i>Gallic acid</i>, <i>Caffeic acid</i>), Saponins</p>	<p>Anti-Inflammatory, Antioxidant, Anti-Bacterial,</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">STEM</p>	<p>Phenolic acids (Gallic acid, Caffeic acid), Triterpenoids, Saponins</p>	<p>Anti-Microbial, Anti-Cancer, Hepatoprotective,</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">FLOWER</p>		<p>Anti-Oxidative, Anti-Cancer Anti-Hyperglycemic, Analgesic, Uv Absorption (Cosmetics), Anti-inflammatory.</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">ROOT</p>	<p>Alkaloids (Blepharin), Terpenoids (Essential oils)</p>	<p>Anti-Inflammatory, Anti-Bacterial Anti-Viral.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">SEED</p>	<p>Saponins, Flavonoids, Essential oils</p>	<p>Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Immunomodulatory.</p>

CONCLUSION:

Spathodea campanulata , *Zizyphus oenoplia* , *Blepharis maderaspatensis* exhibits significant ethnomedicinal, pharmacological, and anticancer potential due to its rich phytochemical composition, including flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and terpenoids. Traditional medicine widely utilizes its extracts for treating various ailments, while scientific studies confirm its antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic activities. Its anticancer properties have been demonstrated through apoptosis induction and cell cycle arrest in multiple cancer cell lines. Despite its promising therapeutic potential, further in-depth pharmacological studies and clinical trials are essential to validate its efficacy and safety for modern cancer treatment.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS:

The author conducted a comprehensive literature review, collected relevant research articles from scientific databases, and analyzed the ethnomedicinal, phytochemical, and anticancer properties of *Spathodea campanulata* , *Zizyphus oenoplia* , *Blepharis maderaspatensis*. The author also compiled and synthesized data on the geographical distribution, traditional medicinal uses, phytochemical constituents, and their mechanisms of action in cancer treatment. Additionally, the author critically evaluated the pharmacological significance of bioactive compounds and their potential application in modern medicine. The manuscript was written, revised, and finalized by the author, ensuring the accuracy and coherence of the information presented.

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